

AWARENESS OF CYBERSTALKING LAW AMONG FACEBOOK AND X (FORMERLY TWITTER) USERS IN OWERRI METROPOLIS, IMO STATE

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ABSTRACT

The major concern that has been raised as a result of the high frequency of social media usage is cyberstalking. In recent times, Facebook and X are flooded with hate speeches, thoughtless comments and unauthorized sharing of personal images and leaving the victims emotionally and mentally drained. cyberstalking has become an alarming and persistent issue on social media, affecting users from all walks of life. While a lot of persons engage in this behaviour, few understand the consequences it carries. This study examined Facebook and X users' level of awareness, extent of knowledge of cyberstalking law in Nigeria and the extent to which their knowledge of cyberstalking law affects their usage of Facebook and X. The Survey research design was used in the study. The sampling procedures used in this study were Purposive and Simple Random sampling. A sample size of 384 was drawn using the Cochran sample determining method. Google form was used as instrument for data collection. SPSS was used to analyze the data. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation. Findings revealed that the respondents were moderately aware of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria; respondents to a moderate extent, have knowledge of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria and that the respondents' knowledge of cyberstalking law in Nigeria have to a large extent influenced their usage of Facebook and X. The study majorly recommended that targeted awareness programs or campaigns on the issue of cyberstalking and the existence of cyberstalking laws in Nigeria should be created.

Keywords: Social media, Awareness, Cyberstalking, Cyberstalking law and Cybersecurity.

Introduction

Evolution in technology has made the world closer than it seems as it enables people interact with each other with no concern about distance. The use of information technologies has shown a very massive growth in almost every country in the world (Akeusola, 2023;). Increasing access to the internet has changed the lives of millions of people who go online on a daily basis.

It has transcended to various forms, one of which is the social media platforms. These platforms include: Facebook, X, Whatsapp, Tiktok (Ibrahim, 2021). These social media platforms have proven to perform exceptionally great in aspects of e-commerce, changing perspectives of business dealings, mutual interactions, keeping in touch with friends and family. Nusaiba (2023) asserts that adding to its purpose of improving personal interactions, social media platforms like Facebook and X have enabled individuals to be engaged in businesses by creatively coming up with marketable ideas through unique content creation strategies. To boost brand awareness among customers, the majority of organisations employ online marketing techniques such as blogger recommendations, advertising on social media etc. (Wang & Kim, 2017).

Nwosu et al (2018) avers that the increased number of cyberspace users in Nigeria has contributed to the rate of cybercrime which is posing a worrisome threat to young people around the globe. Thus, there is a dark side to this increased internet usage. According to Statista (2022), a known global database organization, Nigeria has approximately 84 million internet users despite economic hardship that has affected the majority of Nigeria severely throughout the years. The Statista report projects that there will be a significant rise of Nigeria internet users from 38 percent as at 2022 to 48 percent in 2027. The anonymous nature of the internet and using communication technologies give room for perpetrators to commit crimes (Nwosu et al, 2018).

Recently, the major concern that has been raised as a result of the magnanimousity of social media is cyberstalking (Richards, 2023). BegottiandMaran (2019) assert that this act is threatening or fear-inducing, involves an invasion of a person's right to privacy and manifests in repeated actions overtime. Section 58 of the Nigeria's Cybercrime Act 2015 defines Cyberstalking as a course of conduct directed at a specific person that would cause a reasonable person to feel fear.

Richards (2023) further asserts that cyberstalking has become an alarming and persistent issue on social media, affecting users from all walks of life. While a lot of persons engage in this behaviour, few understand the consequences it carries. In recent times, social media platforms like Facebook and X are flooded with hate speeches, thoughtless comments and unauthorized sharing of personal images and leaving the victims emotionally and mentally drained. It is worthy of note that there have been reported cases where victims of cyberstalking fall into depression, fear, anxiety, social isolation and suicidal ideation (Akeusola, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

In recent times, Cyberstalking has been on the increase especially on Facebook and X (formerly known as Twitter). (Richards, 2023). People feel unsafe these days creating contents or relaying information on social media because of this issue of cyberstalking.

In Nigeria, cyberstalking has emerged as a dominant online threat, with individuals frequently experiencing harassment, intimidation and privacy violations on social media platforms such as Facebook and X. Akeusola (2023) asserts that there is a law on cyberstalking in Nigeria which could be seen in Section 24 of the cybercrimes Act 2015, what cyberstalking entails and the punishments for cyberstalking are all enshrined in this law. Despite the existence of cyberstalking legislation in Nigeria, which is aimed at protecting citizens from such digital abuse, there is still rise in cyberstalking on social media platforms especially Facebook and X. The question posed is; to what level are Facebook and X users aware of the cyberstalking law?

The growing incidence of cyberstalking on social media specifically Facebook and X in Nigeria reveals a research gap that requires further attention. Existing literature primarily focuses on cyberbullying, challenges of cyberbullying. There seem to be a dearth of empirical studies on cyberstalking as well as the awareness of the existing law on cyberstalking in Nigeria. It is based on this that the researchers through this study, empirically examined the awareness level of Facebook and X users on cyberstalking law in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is Facebook and X users' level of awareness on cyberstalking law in Nigeria?
2. What is the extent of knowledge of Facebook and X users on cyberstalking law in Nigeria?

3. To what extent has Facebook and X users' knowledge of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria influenced their usage of Facebook and X?

Literature Review

Social media refers to the set of interactive internet applications that facilitate creation, curation and sharing of user-generated content. Obayi, et al (2024) assert that social media is part of new technologies that have the capacity to mobilize people for a particular cause. The use of social networks is increasingly central to everyday life in that these platforms have proven to be inevitable as they are tools through which people interact with each other.

The emergence of social media began in the early days of internet when people started sharing information and communicating with each other. It was just that the earlier platforms were more “technology” intensive and required some expertise to use and hence the number of people using these platforms was limited. Over a period of time, as the technology matured, platforms were developed where regular users, without any technological background, could also use the services (Varinder & Kanwar, 2019). This was a turning point in the history of internet, making the internet technology all inclusive, where people were no longer silent spectators to the content being served to them. In this dispensation, individuals can now create their own contents, share it with others and as well make money from the contents.

Social media platforms like Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), WhatsApp etc came into existence as a result of the way the internet was used by individuals who loved to network, share content, upload or download files and share them online with friends and also liked to keep in touch with the updated news of their contacts. Thus, the concept of “social networking” took shape in the form of several websites that offered such “networking” features (Cavezza & McEwan, 2014).

Facebook was launched in the year 2004 as a social networking site founded by Mark Zuckerberg and a few of his colleagues. Facebook allows users to create individual profiles, add or invite friends, exchange messages, join other communities of like-minded people or form groups of their own based on common interests. Since its inception, Facebook has evolved in many ways making it much more user-friendly, accessible and a fun place to connect with friends or even strangers with common interests. Its growth has been fueled by strategic acquisitions, including Instagram in 2012 and WhatsApp in 2014, expanding its user base and portfolio (Abiodun, 2021). Adediran (2020) asserts that Facebook has in recent times faced criticism over privacy concerns and its role in spreading misinformation. The scholar further avers that these controversies have led to regulatory scrutiny and calls for increased accountability.

On the other hand, X which was formerly known as Twitter was created in 2006 and has become one of the most popular social media platforms in the world. According to Rodriguez and Keane (2023), X is a social media platform that allows users to share short messages known as “tweets” with their followers. Tweets can be up to 280 characters long and can include text, images, videos and links to other contents on the web. Users can follow other X users to see their tweets in their timelines, and they can also interact with tweets by liking, retweeting and replying to them. X is used by individuals, businesses and organizations to share information, promote products or services, and engage with their audience.

Moreso, the Internet has improved global interactions and made the world a global village with the free exchange of information, ideas, skills, culture and technology (Owe et al., 2023). However, it also raises a number of personal security risks. Some internet users (for various reasons) prey on other users and cause havoc which affects not only personal interests but also commercial concerns and this is termed “Cyberstalking”. Ndubueze, et al (2017) define cyberstalking as the act of threatening, harassing, or annoying someone through multiple messages, as through the Internet, especially with the intent of

placing the recipient in fear that an illegal act or an injury will be inflicted on the recipient or a member of the recipient's family or household. Cyberbullying occurs when someone is bullied, harassed, humiliated, threatened, embarrassed, intimidated, or targeted in some way through the use of information technology such as e-mail, instant messaging, chat rooms, pagers, cell phones or any other online services (Adediran, 2020). Cyberbullying has been called “a social online terror”, “a deadly epidemic”, “a nightmare that happens all too often,” and the cause of youth suicides. Cyberstalking is becoming a common phenomenon in Nigeria as more people engage in it especially on social media platforms (Abiodun, 2021).

Section 24 of the Cybercrimes Act 2015 specifically addressed cyberstalking. It defines cyberstalking as the use of electronic communication to persistently harass, threaten, or intimidate someone. Adediran (2020) argues that the Cybercrimes Act of 2015, was introduced to provide a legal framework for dealing with various forms of cybercrimes, including cyberstalking. The Act recognizes the severity of cyberstalking and other cyber offences, providing a comprehensive guideline for law enforcement agencies to investigate and prosecute such cases. Section 24 of this act stipulates laws that condemn every form of cyberstalking. The contents of this offence are, that the message is very unpleasant or of an unseemly attribute; and it is conveyed for the sole aim of causing anger, troubles, problems to another or causes such an idea to be conveyed. The Act stipulates the penalty for the misdeed as sum of not less than Two Million Naira or imprisonment for a term of not less than one year. (Cohen-Almagor & Trotter, 2022).

Moreso, section 58 of the Act stipulates that cyberstalking includes an action made specifically for a person that may cause someone who is sensible to be afraid. Egwu et al (2022) aver that the acts that come within the confines of this offence may also include sending multiple e-mails, often on a systematic basis, to annoy, embarrass, intimidate, or threaten a person or to make the person fearful that she or a member of her family or household will be harmed.

Egwu et al (2022) argue that the provision of the Cybercrime Act relates to cyberstalking and this provision has been largely criticised by many Nigerians including legal practitioners. The criticisms centers around the argument that the provision is a violation of the right to freedom of expression entrenched in the Nigerian Constitution. The provision has even been challenged in the court of law for violation the Constitution.

Empirical Review

Certain empirical studies seem to be relevant to this study and at such were x-rayed and evaluated in relation to these research objectives.

Ndubueze, Hussein and Sarki (2017) carried out a study that examined the level of awareness of cyberstalking among undergraduate students in Nigeria. The theoretical point of reference adopted is the Routine Activity Theory. The survey research design was adopted for the study. A total of 350 students from Federal University Dutse were sampled using Cluster, Quota and Convenience techniques. Questionnaire and In-depth interview guide served as instrument for data collection. The quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS. The study showed that an average number of the students sampled (58.4%) were conversant with cyberstalking and aware of the variables that constitute it. From their findings, it is pertinent to note that an average number of the students sampled were aware of cyberstalking.

Rajesh and Suriakala (2019) carried out research titled; analytical study on cyberstalking awareness among women using data mining techniques. This study focused on checking the awareness of women on cyberstalking and as well create more awareness on cyberstalking amongst women. It also discussed how women should protect themselves from various kinds of cyber harassment evolving in recent years. The study adopted quantitative and qualitative approaches and employed questionnaire and

interview guide as instrument for data collection. The Visualization tool was used to bring out the association between the women based on the categories and the awareness which they have on cyberstalking. The findings of the study showed that majority of the respondents make use of Social Networking Sites but are not highly aware of cyberstalking.

In another study by Obiaku (2021) the issue of knowledge of cyberbullying was explored. The study was; Portrayal of Cyberbullying in Nigeria: a content analysis of Nigerian newspaper. The study undertook a content analysis approach of content analysing how cyberbullying is portrayed and as well how the portrayal influences the knowledge level of the audience. The researcher examined three newspapers, Thisday, Vanguard and Punch using a qualitative content analysis and frame analysis to examine how the Nigerian media portrays cyberbullying. The findings of the study showed that the issue of cyberbullying is not given prominence and not fully portrayed. The researcher concluded that the lack of full portrayal invariably makes the level of audience knowledge on the issue of discourse low.

In same vein, Erdogdu and Kocyigit (2021) carried out a study on the correlation between social media use and cyber victimization: A research on generation Z in Turkey. In this study, the researchers examined whether there is a meaningful correlation between social media usage and cyber victimization. The cyber victimization levels of the users were investigated using the data of research conducted online with 390 participants (Generation Z) and social media users. The Purposive sampling method was used to select the participants. In the analysis of the data, frequency analysis, pearson correlation analysis and linear regression analysis were performed using the statistical package program. The findings revealed that there were significant correlations at $p=.01$ and $p=.05$ levels between the independent variables of the sub-dimensions of the social media usage scale and the dependent variables of the cyber victimization sub-dimension.

Theoretical Framework

The Diffusion of Innovation Theory: this theory is highly relevant to understanding Facebook and X users' awareness of cyberstalking law in Nigeria. Richards (2023) asserts that this theory propounded by Everett Rogers in 1962, explores how new ideas, behaviors, or technologies spread and are adopted within a social system or society. In line with the study, the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI) provides a framework for understanding how awareness or knowledge about legal regulations diffuses among individuals and communities. This theory enables one gain insights into the dynamics of knowledge dissemination and adoption within online communities which is in relation to this present study.

Methodology

This study adopted the Survey research design. Google form was the instrument for data collection. Google form is an online survey form suitable for this study in that it is targeted at internet (Facebook and X) users. The area of study is Owerri Metropolis and it consists; Owerri Municipal, Owerri North and Owerri West, with a population of 1,023,000 (Statista, 2022). 1,023,000 formed the population of the study. Owerri Metropolis was chosen for this study because of the perceived high level of social media usage amongst its residents. A sample size of 384 was drawn from the population using Cochran sample determining method. The formula is as follows:

$$n_0 = Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1-p) \div e^2$$

where n_0 = sample size

$z = 1.96$ (confidence level)

$$p= 0.5 \text{ (proportion)}$$

$$e= 0.05 \text{ (margin of error)}$$

$$n_0= (1.96)^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot (1-0.5) \div (0.05)^2$$

$$n_0= 3.8416 \times 0.25 \div 0.0025$$

$$n_0= 0.9604 \div 0.0025$$

$$n_0= 384.16 \text{ approximately } 384$$

Purposive and Simple Random sampling techniques were used in this study because the researchers sought to collect data from respondents who are Facebook and X users. The reliability of the instrument was tested using test retest by sending out the Google form to 20 respondents, and the reliability coefficient was checked through the Pearson reliability coefficient, which was 0.85 and this shows a high level of reliability. The Google form was sent to online groups of Owerri Metropolis residents. With that, the researchers were able to control to a large extent, the distribution of the Google form within the area of this study.

The respondents filled the Google form and submitted. Their responses were captured in the form's data base. This enabled the researchers collect the data for analysis. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data that was collected. Tables were used to present the data.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Out of 384 respondents sampled, 377 copies of the form were retrieved. The response rate was 97%. The analysis presented below was done with 370 copies as 7 persons responses were dropped at some point since they were not aware of the cyberstalking law and were not eligible to answer further.

Bio data

Table 1:Bio-data of respondents Distribution

	Options	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	175	46.4%
	Female	202	53.6%
	Total	377	100%
Age	18-25	57	15.1%
	26-35	145	38.4%
	36-45	88	23.3%
	46 and above	87	23.0%
	Total	377	100%
Qualification	SSCE	52	13.7%
	OND/NCE	20	5.3%
	BSc/HND	130	34.4%
	Others	175	46.4%
	Total	377	100%

Source: Field survey, 2024

Data analysis from the above table 1 showed that 53.6% of the respondents are female which means that there were more female in the study. Meanwhile, the respondents between the age ranges of 26-35 were more in the study with the percentage of 38.4%. Furthermore, respondents who indicated others in their response were more with 46.4%. The implication of the analysis is that it shows the distribution of respondents that participated in the study.

Psychographical Data

RQ 1: What is Facebook and X users’ level of awareness on cyberstalking law in Nigeria?

Table 2: Facebook and X users’ level of awareness on cyberstalking law in Nigeria

Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	STD	X	Decision
I get and disseminate information on Facebook and X (formerly Twitter).	159	134	52	32	377	.94263	3.1	Accepted
I am aware that Cyber harassments, cyber threats, cyber insults, cyber defamation are rampant on Facebook and X.	182	151	42	2	377	.69752	3.3	Accepted
I am aware that the cyber harassments, insults and threats that people face on Facebook and X regularly can be referred to as cyberstalking	139	196	41	1	377	.65142	3.2	Accepted
	EA	MA	SA	NA	N	STD	X	Decision
To what extent are you aware of the law on cyber harassments, insults, threats and defamation in Nigeria?	77	178	115	7	377	.75235	2.8	Accepted
	VO	O	R	NA				
How often do you encounter discussions or information about the law on cyber harassments, insults, threats and defamation in Nigeria?	79	99	182	10	370	.83497	2.6	Accepted
Grand Mean							3.0	Accepted

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree,D=Disagree, SD=Strongly Disagree, N=Total frequency
 STD=Standard Deviation
 X=Mean
 EA=Extremely aware, MA=Moderately aware, SA=Slightly aware, NA=Not aware

The results in Table 2 above show that respondents agreed to all the items with a mean range of 2.6 to 3.3. The grand mean rating of Table 2 is 3.0, which is agreeable and implies that Facebook and X users’ level of awareness on cyberstalking law in Nigeria is moderate. The standard deviation ranged from .65142 to .94263, which showed that the respondents were not far from each other in their responses with respect to Facebook and X users’ level of awareness on cyberstalking law in Nigeria.

RQ 2: What is the extent of knowledge of Facebook and X users on cyberstalking law in Nigeria?

Table 3: The extent of knowledge of Facebook and X users on cyberstalking law in Nigeria

Items	E	M	L	VL	N	STD	X	Decision
How would you rate your current understanding of the law on cyber harassment, cyber insults, cyber threats, cyber defamation in Nigeria	48	180	74	68	370	.93570	2.5	Accepted
	SA	A	D	SD	N	STD	X	
I know to a large extent that harassment, threats, insults, false accusations, defamation, slander and libel on the cyber space or internet are considered cyberstalking under Nigerian law	149	161	32	28	370	.87566	3.1	Accepted
I know that there are legal consequences for engaging in defamation, threats, insults on the cyber space in Nigeria	129	175	41	25	370	.84919	3.1	Accepted
I know that I can be jailed or fined when I threaten, insult and abuse people on internet (Facebook and X)	168	118	61	23	370	.91797	3.1	Accepted
Grand Mean						2.9		Accepted

Key: E=Excellent, M=Moderate, L=Limited, VL=Very limited

The results in Table 3 above show that respondents agreed to all the items with a mean range of 2.5 to 3.1. The grand mean rating of Table 3 is 2.9, which is agreeable and implies that the extent of knowledge of Facebook and X users on cyberstalking law in Nigeria is moderate. The standard deviation ranged from .84919 to .93570, which showed that the respondents were not far from each other in their responses with regard to the extent of knowledge of Facebook and X users on cyberstalking law in Nigeria.

RQ 3: To what extent has Facebook and X users’ knowledge of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria influenced their usage of Facebook and X?

Table 4: The extent Facebook and X users’ knowledge of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria have influenced their usage of Facebook and X

Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	STD	X	Decision
I am very cautious about my discussions on Facebook and X due to the existence of the law on cyber harassment, cyber insults, cyber threats, cyber defamation in Nigeria.	143	161	40	26	370	.87105	3.1	Accepted
I have refrained from engaging in certain discussions on	129	180	43	18	370	.80183	3.1	Accepted

Facebook and X because of my knowledge of the existing law on cyber harassment, cyber insults, cyber threats, cyber defamation in Nigeria								
My knowledge on cyberstalking law in Nigeria has influenced my behaviour on Facebook and X.	139	175	31	25	370	.84087	3.1	Accepted
Knowledge on Cyberstalking law in Nigeria has made me more conscious of potential risks and consequences associated with online behaviour on Facebook and X.	118	168	51	33	370	.90317	3.0	Accepted
Grand Mean							2.9	Accepted

The results in Table 4 above show that respondents agreed to all the items with a mean range of 3.0 to 3.1. The grand mean rating of Table 4 is 3.0, which is agreeable and implies that the extent of Facebook and X users’ knowledge of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria have to a large extent influenced their usage of Facebook and X. The standard deviation ranged from .80183 to .90317, which showed that the respondents were not far from each other in their responses with regard to the extent of how Facebook and X users’ knowledge of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria have influenced their usage of the platforms.

Discussion of Findings

The findings with respect to research question 1 revealed that the respondents were moderately aware of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria. This simply showed that their level of awareness was not so high and as well not low. Their level of awareness could be linked to the moderate level of their educational attainment as seen in the demographic data (see table 1). This finding supports the assertion of Ndubueze, Hussein & Sarki (2017) who carried out a study that examined the awareness and perception of undergraduate students on cyberstalking. They aver that an average number (58.4%) of respondents were conversant with cyberstalking and aware of the variables that constitute it. The finding of this study is also in line with the assertion of Rajesh & Suriakala (2019) who examined cyberstalking awareness among women using data mining techniques. Their study showed that majority of the respondents make use of Social Networking Sites (SNS) but are not highly aware of cyberstalking.

Findings in research question two revealed that respondents to a moderate extent have knowledge of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria. This finding is in relation to the Diffusion of Innovation theory which explains that one gains insights into the dynamics of knowledge dissemination and adoption within online communities. This knowledge would guide their conduct and help them adhere to the law. In contrast to the present study, Obiaku (2021) asserts that the knowledge level of audience on cyberstalking is low. This contrast may be as a result of slight progress in enlightenment over the years.

Findings in research question 3 showed that the respondents’ knowledge of cyberstalking law in Nigeria have to a large extent influenced their usage of Facebook and X. Since their extent of knowledge from the findings is moderate, it simply implies that the influence their knowledge has on their usage of Facebook and X is moderate. This resonates with the Diffusion of Innovation theory. This theory further adds that the level of knowledge about a topic influences attitudes towards that topic, which in turn influence behavior. Therefore, since the knowledge level on cyberstalking laws in Nigeria is moderate, it would likely lead to a moderate level of usage as individuals’ attitudes and behaviors are influenced by their level of knowledge.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is obvious that the respondents are aware and knowledgeable of the cyberstalking law in Nigeria, but their moderate level of awareness and knowledge is not impressive and efficient. It simply implies that their current state of awareness and knowledge may not be sufficient to enable them abide by the said laws. It is important to note that social media users are expected to be fully aware and highly knowledgeable of the legal consequences of cyberstalking in Nigeria.

Recommendations

In line with the findings, it was therefore recommended that:

1. Targeted awareness programs or campaigns on the issue of cyberstalking and the existence of cyberstalking laws in Nigeria should be created.
2. Nigerian government should collaborate with social media influencers and content creators, leveraging their platforms to disseminate information about cyberstalking laws and promote positive online behaviors.

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